

Oracle AutoTask enhancement for multi-database environment

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Project Specification

The goal of my project was to develop a tool for facilitating controlling internal Oracle database maintenance jobs. Optionally I was proposed to extend the tool with additional components for controlling of other database related settings. The tool had to be easily customizable, work in multi-database environment and provide concise report for further review to in order to facilitate database administration.

Abstract

Document describes DBCheck – reporting tool for multi-database environment. In particular document describes architecture of a tool, detailed description of verifications made, customization and reports provided. Last part of a document contains short manual about tool usage and reference to further documentation.

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Introduction

Databases are important for everyday CERN operation. They are used for two main purposes:

- To store part of experiments metadata (like conditions of detectors and its environment)
- To store data related to make CERN operational as a company (like administration data)

Databases are not only used because of their reliability of preserving data, but also because of their speed of extracting data when needed. The key component that provides performance of database queries in Oracle databases is cost-based query optimizer. Such optimizer needs various statistics about database and its objects. Such statistics are gathered by internal database jobs. Having fresh optimizer statistics is crucial for database performance.

Oracle 11g added a new component called Autotask. It is a central component responsible for management of scheduled maintenance tasks, such like gathering optimizer statistics. New release of Oracle database software, which IT-DB is going to migrate to in 2013/2014, introduces even more new features of optimizer statistics. Therefore there is a growing need for having more detailed control of Optimizer statistics gathering strategy.

The goal of my project was to develop a tool for controlling internal Oracle database maintenance jobs. The tool had to be easily customizable, work in multi-database environment and provide concise report which can be later reviewed by database administration.

Optionally I was proposed to extend the tool with additional components for controlling other database related settings. Such tool existed before in IT-DB section, so my work in this area is based on this.

I was proposed to extend the tool with additional components for controlling

In this document I want to describe the architecture of newly created DBCheck tool and provide manual to tool usage.

DBCheck Architecture

The main goal of new tool architecture was to have modularity. The purpose of this is to give as much freedom as possible to module creator.

Main DBCheck entity acts as an orchestrator – it gets argument from a command line, runs specified module and saves generated report in common directory for all modules.

The tool functionality is encoded in modules. Each module has to provide only `text_report()` method (which is used to generate report). Module internals are left for the module creator, so they can be customized for specific needs of particular module.

Currently developed modules consist of series of checks. Checks are non-divisible entities, which performs single verification inside module. Such module architecture is recommended for future modules.

Each module can be customized by configuration files (called templates). There are 3 things to be customized: logic of checks, list of databases to perform checks and exceptions which don't have to satisfy given check.

Description of modules

Autotask

Description

The goal in developing module was to automatize maintenance task with checking parameters and behavior of jobs defined by Autotask scheduler.

Module consists of series of checks which consist part of module logic.

Every check implements methods `is_correct()` and `text_report()` -- they are used in main Module class to produce report for the whole module. The composition of all checks is done by Module class in `module.py`

Implementation

Module uses `cx_Oracle` to connect to Oracle databases and invoke a series of SQL statements on database.

Module uses list of databases and their TNS names provided by script `/ORA/dbs01/syscontrol/bin/oracletab.sh`

SQL queries used by module can be found in file `query_repository_autotask.py`

Templates used by this module are read by `ConfigParser` python module (syntax of templates is similar to `.ini` files).

Checks performed

- Autotask Stats Job: checks if autotask stats gathering job (job name: auto optimizer stats collection) is set the same as in `checks_template` (enabled, disabled or enabled/disabled).
- Autotask Space Advisor: checks if autotask space advisor job (job name: auto space advisor) is set the same as in `checks_template` (enabled, disabled or enabled/disabled).
- Autotask Tuning Advisor: checks if autotask tuning advisor job (job name: sql tuning advisor) is set the same as in `checks_template` (enabled, disabled or enabled/disabled).
- Stats History Retention: checks if stats history retention time (in days) is not smaller than defined in template
- Stats Job History: checks if at least one of the k last stats jobs ended with success, where k is the number defined in template
- Active Scheduler Windows: checks if active scheduler windows used for autotask maintenance jobs are defined the same as in template
- Active Window Wrong: tries to close incorrectly opened windows - if manage to close one informs in it in report

Base_DB

Description

The goal in developing module was to automatize maintenance task with checking parameters and behaviour of jobs defined by Autotask scheduler.

Module consists of series of checks which consist part of module logic.

Every check implements methods `is_correct()` and `text_report()` -- they are used in main Module class to produce report for the whole module. The composition of all checks is done by Module class in `module.py`

Implementation

Module uses `cx_Oracle` to connect to Oracle databases and invoke a series of SQL statements on database.

Module uses list of databases and their TNS names provided by script `/ORA/dbs01/syscontrol/bin/oracletab.sh`

SQL queries used by module can be found in file `query_repository_base.py`

Templates used by this module are read by `ConfigParser` python module (syntax of templates is similar to `.ini` files).

Checks performed

- Parameters: Check various parameters defined in template. Value of every parameter can be provided by SQL style condition in a template.
- Properties: Check various properties defined in template. Value of every parameter can be provided by SQL style condition in a template (similar as in Parameters check)
- SGA General Allocation: For given `sga_max_size` checks if `db_cache_size` and `shared_pool_size` are not less than given percent of `sga_max_size`.
- SGA Target: Check if SGA Target size is equal zero or equal SGA Max size.
- SGA Free Memory: Check if SGA Free Memory is equal to zero.
- Parameters Consistency: Check if parameter values are the same between different database instances.
- System Tablespace: Check if there are any segments allocated in SYSTEM tablespace. Users specified in template are allowed to have such segments.

Base_OS

Description

The main goal of module is to check operating system settings of machines running database instances.

`Base_OS` module consists of a series of checks. Every check is non-divisible entity that contains part of module logic. Check files are contained in directory checks

Every check implements methods `is_correct()` and `text_report()` -- they are used in main Module class to produce report for the whole module. The composition of all checks is done by Module class in file `module.py`

Implementation

Module uses `paramiko` library to connect and perform checks by SSH protocol.

Module uses list of databases and hosts respective for the databases provided by script `/ORA/dbs01/syscontrol/bin/oracletab.sh`

Templates used by this module are read by `ConfigParser` python module (syntax of templates is similar to `.ini` files).

Checks performed

- Mountpoints: If machine is running ASM the result of check is OK. If machine is not running ASM it checks if every mountpoint defined in template exists on machine.

Backup

Description

The main goal of module is to check various settings connected with database backups & recovery.

Backup module consists of a series of checks. Every check is non-divisible entity that contains part of module logic. Check files are contained in directory checks

Every check implements methods `get_result()` and `text_report()` -- they are used in main Module class to produce report for the whole module. The composition of all checks is done by Module class in file `module.py`

Implementation

Module uses `cx_Oracle` to connect to Oracle databases and invoke a series of SQL statements on database.

Module uses list of databases and their TNS names provided by script `/ORA/dbs01/syscontrol/bin/oracletab.sh`

SQL queries used by module can be found in file `query_repository_backup.py`

Templates used by this module are read by `ConfigParser` python module (syntax of templates is similar to `.ini` files).

Some of the checks for this module are performed using bash commands (like `grep`, `sed`).

Checks performed

1. Backup scheduled: check if all needed backups are scheduled
2. Recovery scheduled: check if all needed automatic recoveries scheduled
3. BCT Used: check if block tracking change is used
4. Offline datafiles: check if there are any offline datafiles
5. RMAN configuration: check if recovery window or other RMAN configuration parameters properly defined
6. Datafiles without backups: check if there any datafiles without backups

Templates

Overview

Templates are the configuration files that provide customization of module. Templates use syntax similar to .ini files.

Checks template

This template is used to customize checks performed. Meaning of template value may vary (because the checks logic also varies a lot) and in case of any uncertainty please consult documentation for a given check.

Connection template

This template is used to customize checked database. One can specify if the check should be performed on all databases (the list of all databases is taken from LDAP), for the specified list of databases or for the databases with given type/domain in LDAP (e.g. production databases with domain castor).

Exception template

This template is used to make an exception for a given check. In cases of most checks one specifies that the whole check will be skipped. Sometimes (e.g. for parameters/property check) one can specify that only part of check can be not fulfilled.

Reports

Overview

Reports provided are stored in a common directory (which is specified in main DBCheck file). Each module generates separate report file with name of module and date of report generation. Further action with report could be performed using external tools e.g.:

- Report scheduling – cron
- Mailing the report – sendmail
- Reviewing the report – using grep

Report syntax is created in a way that makes it easy to review (with tools like grep).

Sample report

```
===== AUTOTASK MODULE =====  
Start Time: 2013-08-20 11:12:05  
Template path: /ORA/dbs03/PDBBACKUP/home/dbcheck/modules/autotask/templates  
Checking Databases listed in template  
Number of checked databases: 2
```

```
cerndb1          2013-08-20 11:12:06  Autotask Stats Job           : OK  
cerndb1          2013-08-20 11:12:06  Autotask Space Advisor       : OK
```

```
cerndb1      2013-08-20 11:12:06 Autotask Tuning Advisor      : OK
cerndb1      2013-08-20 11:12:06 Stats History Retention     : OK
cerndb1      2013-08-20 11:12:06 Stats Job History           : OK
cerndb1      2013-08-20 11:12:06 Active Scheduler Windows    : OK (SKIPPED)
cerndb1      2013-08-20 11:12:06 Active Window Wrong         : OK

test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Autotask Stats Job          : OK
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Autotask Space Advisor     : OK
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Autotask Tuning Advisor     : OK
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Stats History Retention     : OK
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Stats Job History           : OK
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Active Scheduler Windows    : FAILED
test2        2013-08-20 11:12:06 Active Window Wrong         : OK
```

statscheck.py

Overview

As my main goal was to create tool for controlling Oracle Autotask component I created statscheck script to make my solution more comprehensive. The script is based on Autotask module, is available on every database host. Statscheck provides detailed information about internal database maintenance jobs. Such information may be used to further diagnose problems indicated by DBCheck.

Information presented

1. Stats gathering manager (either DBMS scheduler or Autotask)
2. Stats history retention setting
3. Job history of Autotask (how long they performed, and if succeeded)
4. Client history of Autotask (how auto optimizer stats performed)
5. Currently running jobs of Autotask
6. All statistics jobs history (either run manually, by DBMS scheduler or by Autotask)
7. Active scheduler windows (name, duration and frequency)
8. Candidate tables for incremental statistics gathering

How to?

Run DBCheck with default templates

- Set db-manager environment

```
set_db-manager
```

- Set DBCHECK_HOME variable

```
export DBCHECK_HOME = /home/database_tools/dbcheck/
```

- Run DBCheck (in example with modules autotask base_db)

```
python main.py autotask base_db
```

Run DBCheck with customized templates

- Set db-manager environment

```
set_db-manager
```

- Set DBCHECK_HOME variable

```
export DBCHECK_HOME = /home/database_tools/dbcheck/
```

- 3 Create custom templates in any directory you want (for example /home/SCOTT/db_check_templates). The easiest way to do it is to copy module templates from modules/module_name/templates and modify them to your needs.

- Run DBCheck (in example with modules autotask base_db)

```
python main.py autotask base_db
```

Browse reports provided by DBCheck

- Reports are saved into directory

```
/ORA/dbs01/syscontrol/local/logs/dbcheck/
```

- Look for report you are interested in – file names correspond to

```
moduleName_report_date_time
```

Appendix

Additional documentation (both for future developers and for user) is provided on DB section TWiki page.